

Effect of surfactants on the kinetics of base – catalyzed hydrolysis of methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl acetates

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The velocity constants of base – catalyzed methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl acetates in aqueous and micellar media are determined at different temperatures. The velocity constants in anionic and non-ionic media are higher than those in aqueous media, whereas the energy of activation are lower. The velocity constants for the alkaline hydrolysis of the esters vary in the order : κ -methyl acetate > κ -ethyl acetate > κ -isopropyl acetate < κ -*n*-butyl acetate.

The interest in catalysis of organic reactions by micelles has increased due to the discovery of similarities between micelles and cell membranes and due to the use of micelles as models for enzyme - catalyzed reactions¹⁻³. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to carry out a systematic investigation on the alkaline hydrolysis of methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl acetates in anionic (sodium dodecyl sulfate SDS), cationic (cetylpyridinium chloride CPC) and non-ionic (Triton X-100) micellar media.

Results and Discussion

The velocity constants (κ) of alkali hydrolysis of methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl acetates were determined at 25, 30 and 35 \pm 0.1 $^\circ$, using conductometric method. All the experiments were repeated twice and the results were reproducible (within the experimental error limits). For the sake of brevity and convenience the summary of the results of only one system at one temperature is given in Table 1.

Base-catalyzed hydrolysis of the acetates in aqueous medium :

In the case of methyl acetate hydrolysis, the plot of $(\lambda_0 - \lambda_t)/(\lambda_t - \lambda_\infty)$ vs time is initially linear, but with the increase in time, a deviation is observed. However, in the titration method, the plot of $(V_0 - V_\infty)/(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs time is linear even up to 60 min. So, it is evident that the observed decrease in conductance of the solution with the increase in time is due to the resultant of the consumption of OH⁻ ions and the slight increase in concentration of acetate ions. Therefore, for calculating the velocity constants, only the initial values of conductances were used. However, in the case of other esters, the deviations (in the plots) started after a longer period. The κ values obtained by conductometric method at 25 $^\circ$ (Table 1) agree with those obtained by titration method. It can be seen from the data that the velocity constant of hydrolysis of methyl acetate is highest

amongst the esters, and the hydrolysis constant decreased when the ester was changed from methyl to ethyl and to isopropyl, similar to the trend reported by Laidler and Chen⁴. Similar trends were reported in the literature of base-catalyzed ethyl benzoate and substituted ethyl benzoates and this trend was explained on the basis of slight difficulty for the nucleophilic agent to attack the carboxyl carbon atoms. However, in the case of alkaline hydrolysis of alkyl halides, such trends were explained on the basis of change in the mechanism of hydrolysis, i.e. from SN₂ to SN₁⁵. It may be noted that the reactivity of esters depends on the electronegativity of the leaving group (R¹ in RCOOR¹). So, the decrease in κ value of methyl acetate to isopropyl acetate can be understood in terms of lower electronegativity of the leaving group (and hindering nucleophilic attack) and higher resonance stabilization of the parent group RCOO⁻. However, the higher κ value of *n*-butyl acetate hydrolysis can not be explained on the basis of the above reasoning.

The velocity constants of base-catalyzed hydrolysis of esters are much higher than those of acid-catalyzed hydrolysis. The higher values of κ indicate that the negatively charged hydroxide ions make the nucleophilic attack more easier. The velocity constants increase with the increase in temperature, and the energy of activation of the above mentioned esters are 61.8, 58.8, 56.0 and 57 \pm 0.6 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively, which are slightly higher than those of acid-catalyzed esters. In acid hydrolysis, as the uncharged water molecule attacks the carbonyl carbon atom, the repulsion energy is slightly lower than that of the hydroxyl ion's attack. The substitution of methyl groups increases the repulsion between the reactants and hence the energy of activation is increased when the methyl group of the ester is substituted by ethyl or isopropyl acetate groups.

Base-catalyzed hydrolysis of the acetates in anionic

Note

micellar media SDS : The alkaline hydrolysis of the acetates were carried out in micellar media of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS; 0.01 M) at 25, 30 and 35°. The slightly higher values of κ (compared to those in aqueous media) (Table 1) indicate that anionic micellar media enhance the rate of hydrolysis of the esters and this trend was observed at all the three temperatures studied. Our attempts to get the reliable information (from the literature) on the base-catalyzed hydrolysis of alkaline esters were not successful (most of the literature data are on the alkaline hydrolysis of aromatic and substituted aromatic esters⁶). The effect of micelles on organic reactions is generally attributed to electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions. In the present case, the simple electrostatic consideration does not seem to be the appropriate model. The solubilization of reactants and their distribution among micelles play the most important role on micelle - catalyzed reactions, particularly when the concentrations of the reactants are greater than the micellar concentrations. The slight increase in rate of hydrolysis may be due to the increase in concentration of the ester in the surface of the micelle (compared to that in the bulk phase), i.e. the locus solubilization of the ester must be such that the reactive site of substrate must be easily accessible to the attacking reagents. For a bimolecular reaction the rate will be determined by the product of the local concentrations. Depending on the reactants and system, this product can be either greater or smaller than that of the bulk concentrations. The slight increase in reaction rate of hydrolysis of ester can be due to the slight excess of concentration of esters on the surface of anionic micelle (due to the electrostatic interaction slightly positive carbon of carbonyl group of ester and negative head group of micelle) compared to that in the bulk solution. The other reason for the higher κ could be due to the changes in micellar structure due to sodium hydroxide itself.

The velocity constant of base - promoted hydrolysis of esters in SDS micellar media decreases from methyl to ethyl to isopropyl acetate, and this is the trend reported for the acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of ester also. However, we do not wish to overemphasize this because in acid media, sodium dodecyl sulfate itself hydrolyses².

The values of energy of activation for the base-catalyzed hydrolysis of the above esters in SDS micellar media are lower than those in aqueous media, i.e. 50, 59, 59 and 48 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. From these lower values of energy of activation, one is tempted to infer that the reaction may be taking place near the interface between the aqueous environment and a polar micellar interior and stabilizes the transition state of the reactions.

Base-catalyzed hydrolysis of the acetates in nonionic surfactant, Triton X-100 :

The velocity constant of alkali hydrolysis of the acetates in nonionic micellar media (Triton X-100, 0.01 M) were determined at 25, 30 and 35°. The values of velocity constants (Table 1) are much higher than those in aqueous or anionic micellar media. Such trends were reported for other esters and an attempt was made to explain such behavior on the basis of hydrophobic interaction^{1,6}. However, we feel that as the micelles are nonionic, the reacting species OH⁻ can easily approach the ester whose local concentrations on the surface of the micelles is higher (than that in the bulk) and the higher concentration of the reactant enhances the rate of the reaction. In addition, the presence of a large number of micelles of Triton-X-100 (compared to those of SDS of the same concentration) may assist the solubilization which in turn may increase the rate of hydrolysis. The other plausible reason could be that the polar part of non-ionic surfactant may assist in stabilization of the transition state. This view can be supported by the fact that the energy

Table 1. Rate constants* for base-catalyzed hydrolysis of carboxylic esters in aqueous and micellar media

Ester	Medium	Velocity constant, κ^{\ddagger} , dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹			E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^{\ddagger} kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^{\ddagger} kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^{\ddagger} J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		κ_{25}	κ_{30}	κ_{35}				
Methyl acetate	Aqueous	1.08×10^{-1}	1.57×10^{-1}	2.26×10^{-1}	61.80	54.00	-183.00	79.00
	SDS	1.43×10^{-1}	1.85×10^{-1}	2.62×10^{-1}	50.00	44.00	-115.00	78.00
	Triton X-100	1.73×10^{-1}	2.29×10^{-1}	2.7×10^{-1}	36.00	32.00	-154.00	77.00
Ethyl acetate	Aqueous	4.3×10^{-2}	7.0×10^{-2}	9.0×10^{-2}	58.80	54.00	-90.00	81.00
	SDS	8.4×10^{-2}	1.22×10^{-1}	1.71×10^{-1}	59.00	52.00	92.00	79.00
	Triton X-100	1.03×10^{-1}	1.48×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-1}	56.00	48.00	-103.00	79.00
Isopropyl acetate	Aqueous	3.3×10^{-2}	3.7×10^{-2}	5.8×10^{-2}	56.00	40.00	-139.00	82.00
	SDS	3.5×10^{-2}	5.1×10^{-2}	7.1×10^{-2}	59.00	52.00	-101.00	81.00
	Triton X-100	3.9×10^{-2}	4.8×10^{-2}	6.2×10^{-2}	38.00	33.00	-162.00	81.00
<i>n</i> -Butyl acetate	Aqueous	1.02×10^{-2}	1.48×10^{-1}	2.0×10^{-1}	57.00	50.00	-95.00	79.00
	SDS	9.0×10^{-2}	1.3×10^{-1}	1.6×10^{-1}	48.00	42.00	-126.00	79.00
	Triton X-100	1.1×10^{-1}	1.4×10^{-1}	1.9×10^{-1}	46.00	39.00	-133.00	79.00

* Average error limits, ± 0.002 .

of activation for the saponification of the above acetates are 36, 56, 38 and 46 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively, which are much lower than those in aqueous/anionic micellar media.

Our attempts to study the base-catalyzed hydrolysis of methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl acetates in cationic micellar media cetylpyridinium chloride, were not successful, because the moment sodium hydroxide solution was added to the ester solutions in cationic micellar media, the solutions became turbid.

From the present investigation, it is evident that the rates of base-catalyzed hydrolysis of carboxylic esters in anionic and nonionic micellar media are higher than those in aqueous media, whereas the energies of activation for hydrolysis are lower.

Experimental

Sodium dodecyl sulfate SDS, CH₃(CH₂)₁₁OSO₃Na⁺ (Glaxo) and cetyl pyridinium chloride CPC, CH₃(CH₂)₁₄-CH₂O₅H₅N⁺Cl⁻ (Aldrich) were crystallized from ethanol-water mixture and dried before use. Triton-X 100, CH₃C(CH₃)₂CH₂(CH₃)₂C₆H₄(OCH₂CH₂)₁₀OH (Sigma) was used as such. Methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl acetates (extra pure, Merck) were used as such. Double-distilled water was used for preparing all the solutions.

Equal volumes (25 ml) of same concentration (0.05 M) of the esters and sodium hydroxide solutions in aqueous/micellar media (0.01 M conc. – above cmc) were mixed at constant temperature (using a thermostat) and the conductivities of the mixed systems were measured at different times. The infinite reading was determined in the usual manner. All the experiments were repeated twice and the average values (which were within the experimental errors) reported. The experiments were carried out at 25, 30, 35 ± 0.1°.

In studying the rate acceleration or inhibitions by the micelle, it is desirable to avoid the use of buffers and

electrolytes (as aggregation number – micelle's size/shape are changed). In the present case, as the reaction is between a neutral molecule and an ion, the influence of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction is very very small and the small change is neglected.

The velocity constant was determined by the titration as well as conductometric methods and the results obtained by the two methods were within the experimental error.

The rate constant was determined using the standard equation,

$$\kappa = 1/at [x/(a - x)]$$

where κ is the velocity constant, a the initial conc. of reactant and x the concentration of product at time t . The energy of activation was determined using Arrhenius equation,

$$\log \kappa_1/\kappa_2 = (-E_a/2.303 R)(1/T_1 - 1/T_2)$$

where κ_1 and κ_2 are the velocity constants at temperatures T_1 and T_2 , respectively.

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